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Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

DR. APOLLO MARR F. BUGAY, RPsy

Instructor 1

Negros Oriental State University

apollo.bugay@norsu.edu.ph

“THE KEYS TO WELL-BEING”

Rhythm, Life, and Happiness
Purpose, and Experiences
Simplicity and Gentleness
Belief in a Supreme Being
These are the keys to well-being

To dream, to hope, and to love
To move and fly free like a dove
To let go of things beyond our control
Pause, Feel, Be Slow, and Reflect
These are the keys to well-being

Being in tune with nature
Have friends for laughter and comfort
Solace, Warmth, and be at Home
Apply all that I am saying
And you will live a life
of good well-being